

The Role of Islamic Education in Moral Character Building of Pakistani Youth: An Analytic Study

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Abstract

This study looks at the importance of Islamic Education in the youth of Pakistan. Our education policies and the constitution of Pakistan (1973) and our various education policies have provided clear indications for the purpose of our education system, which should be based on Islamic principles. Pakistan was established with a two-state perspective. There are many topics on which Pakistan was founded on the basis of dualism. In Pakistan, Islamic studies for most people are also the main syllabus of Islamic schools or Madaris in the country. These Islamic schools or Madaris cater mainly to young people on a poor class and those who are learning to become Islamic pastors. It is considered important in the moral development of Muslim students attending Pakistani schools because it is a religious matter. In this study, an attempt was made to analyze the effectiveness of Islamic education in the education system and to analyze the student's views on Islamic education as a tool for character development. Islamic education helps students to become good citizens and plays a positive role in their lives. Islamic education undoubtedly has a profound impact on the lives of students and makes them very useful in their community and moreover, this helps the youth of Pakistan in its educational process. Islamic education can be passed on to the efforts of the Muslim community who taught themselves, to pass on the legacy of Islamic knowledge, especially through its main sources, the Quran and Sunnah. There are two major educational programs in the country of modern education and religious education. The country's education policy ensures the transformation of an integrated national education system by bringing Deni Madaris and modern schools closer to each stream in the curriculum and content of education.

Introduction

It is true that Pakistan is a state of ideology, therefore, a constant choice should be given to such recommendations that help to strengthen the value of Islamic education. In addition to the recommendation contained in the study that digestion that enlightens the views of the people and the Pakistani organization will also be included in the study in the hope that this will give a brief moment of reflection to both government officials and clergy. Islamic studies are a compulsory subject in the Pakistani education system and are taught from the lowest to the highest levels. The article contains important information needed to maintain Islamic faith and values. We cannot underestimate its great impact on society. This article enables Muslims to carry out their religious duties and to protect their culture (Florida 2014). Islamic education undoubtedly has a profound impact on the life of the student and makes them the maximum beneficial human being of their society and moreover, that is beneficial for college students of their studying process. (Benagli, 1998).

Islamic education plays an important role in shaping characters and makes the student aware of their social responsibilities. It also binds their confidence to deal with problems and problems in their own lives. Above all the purpose of the creation of Pakistan was to live their lives according to Islamic teaching. (Ziring, 1984). Pakistan was the first empire created in the name of Islam. About 98% of the population is Muslim and believe in Islamic monotheism. Muslims view education as a form of worship (ibadah) in which Muslims share the same values based on the Quran and Sunnah.

1.1 Education System in Pakistan

When Pakistan become based in 1947, it offered five educational system reports. These are:

1. Educational Convocation
2. National Education committee
3. Current Educational Policy
4. Educational policy

In the Education Policy of Pakistan in 1998-2010 the purpose and objectives of the teaching of Islamic Education make it clear that "Education and training should allow the citizens of Pakistan to lead themselves according to Islamic coaching as set out with inside the Qur'an and Sunnah and to teach and teach them as a practicing real Muslim. Transforming an integrated national education system by bringing Deeni Madaris and modern schools closer to each stream in the curriculum and education content. In Grade VIII he introduced the Nazra Qur'an as a compulsory subject while at a higher level a translation of selected verses from the Holy Qur'an would be provided.

1.2 Secondary Education in Pakistan

Secondary and secondary schooling begins in Pakistan from ninth grade at the beginning of the 10th grade, students take exams which are limited to the critical and secondary schooling Board (BISE). After efficaciously completing their checks, college students are offered a 'matric' course at a time whilst the scholars are ready to go into different faculties to compete for grades eleven and twelve (11th and twelfth) is referred to as Inter lessons. Once they complete grade 12, in addition they take tests on regional boards. Upon successful of completion of this take a look at, college students were presented a better Secondary school (HSC) certificate. This level of training is likewise known as F. A / F.Sc or middle. Throughout these classes students have a desire of pre-clinical, pre-engineering, pc technology and so on.

1.3 Madras or Religious Faculty Schooling in Pakistan

In Pakistan, there are numerous sorts of spiritual establishments wherein simplest the Qur'an is taught, Mosque faculties wherein both are taught the Quran and different subjects in Madaris in which most effective Islamic getting to know takes location. The motive of maximum madrasas in Pakistan is to prepare the pupil for religious activities. in step with robust spiritual teachings, Madaris and Islamic studies together with the Qur'an, Islamic regulation and regulation, common sense and the traditions of the Prophet. Depending on the level of the madrassa (first, center or higher) the awareness of spiritual teachings will increase. Hafiz-e-Qur'an (someone who memorizes the Quran) or Qari (who can recite the Quran through pronunciation and accurate tone) are produced at the bottom degree of the Madrassas. A certificate of purpose from Madrassa is equivalent to an MA degree in Islamic studies or Arabic from a regular university. A Madrassa excessive faculty graduate is prepared to claim Fatwas - non secular regulation. Complete-time college students enrolling in Madrassas achieve this with the expertise that they will handiest be gifted in spiritual research and will get a activity within the area of religion because only a few people in Madrassas are enrolled in theology. (Uzma Anzar: 2003: 14-16)

There are five primary Islamic schools of idea in Pakistan: Deobandi, Bareli, Ahle-Hadith, Salafi and Shia. All of this has their Madrassas as coaching of their personal Islam. Thetwo main sects of Sunni Islam are Deobandi and Bareli. Deobandi sectors are taken into consideration the most obedient and anti-western. The primary spiritual curriculum for the madrassas of Pakistan is just like different Madrassas within the world besides that it had few books in Pakistan. It focuses on coaching Islam - Hadith, Fiqa, Tafseer, Dunna and like. a regular instance of what's taught in Madrassas schools in Pakistan is provided as follows:

In First Year, Biography of the Prophet (Syrat), Conjugation-Grammar (Sarf), Syntax (Nahv), Arabic Literature, Chirography, Chant illation (Tajwid)

In Second year, Conjugation-Grammar (Sarf), Syntax (Nahv), Arabic Literature, Jurisprudence (Fiqa). Good judgment, Chirography (Khush-navies). Chant illation (Tajwid)

In Third year, Quranic Exegesis, Jurisprudence (Fiqa), Syntax (Nahv), Arabic Literature, Hadith common sense, Islamic Brotherhood, external study

In Fourth Year, Quranic Exegesis, Jurisprudence (Fiqa), Principle of Jurisprudence, Rhetoric's, Hadith, common sense, History, Can't illation, current Sciences

In Fifth Year, Quranic Exegesis, Jurisprudence (Fiqa), precept of Jurisprudence, Rhetoric's, Belief's (Aqa'id), common sense, Arabic Literature, Philosophy, Chant illation, external look

In Sixth Year, Interpretation of the Qur'an, Jurisprudence, Principles of Interpretation & jurisprudence, Arabic Literature, Philosophy, Chant illation, Study of Prophet's tradition

In seventh year, Sayings of the Prophet, Jurisprudence, Belief (Aqa'ed), Responsibility (Fra'iz) Chant illation, External study

In Eight Year, ten books by various authors focusing on the sayings of the Prophet. (Course Content Dar-Ul-Uloom Dew band)

Consistent with authorities' figures, there are currently eleven, 491 madrasas in united

States of America, despite the fact that unlawful assets set this range at 12,000 to 15000 the entire student quantity of college students is 1 million. Training data in Pakistan offer the total quantity of madras students 1.518 million out of 140,031 million counted as Takhassus

There are some main madrasas in Pakistan

- Wafaq-ul-Madaris Deobandi Multan 1959
- Tanzim-ul-Madaris Bareli Lahore 1960

- Wafaq-ul-Madaris Shia Lahore 1959
- Rabitatul-Madaris-al-Islamia Jannat-e-Islami Lahore 1983 Wafaq-ul-Madaris-al-salafia Ahl-e-Hadith Faisalabad 1955 (Education system in Pakistan 2006:26)

Islamic Concept of Value

Worth in Islam is a fashion on which we judge a pastime to be accurate or incorrect. These equipment's are also beneficial to distinguish genuine and evil deeds. The Islamic machine is immutable and does not change by using given any extrude with time clearly. Due to the truth Allah is immutable and the universe is jogging under per meant criminal recommendations and thoughts given with the resource of using Allah. Islam has its personal ethical, social, political, civil and comparatively cheap values, which might be discussed as under:

Social Values:

The human relationships are continually governed by means of social values. In step with Islam all values affecting man need to be based totally upon the Qur'anic idea that every man or woman is endowed by using the Allah with high potential for doing excellent on himself and to his society, and his personality need to be reputable. In Qur'an Allah says that Allah distinguished mankind into tribes and country for the energy of sex. The real and true deliver of privilege with sides the sight of Allah says, and authentic supply of honor in the sight of Allah is a righteous lifestyle as Allah says,

O mankind, we've got created you from male and girl, and made you united states of America and tribes you can apprehend each other. The noblest of you inside in the sight of Allah is he who nice in behavior. Lo Allah is the first-rate knower. (Surah Al- Hujurat Verse No-thirteen)

Equality in Islam:

During farewell cope with, Muhammad (Sallallahu Alaihi Wasallam) said,

Are all brothers and are identical not one of the, can claim any honors or any superiority over any others?

The concept of regularly occurring brotherhood I set up through Islam. Quran harassed that a real brotherhood can be made best through distinctive feature of mankind's courting with one another and different elements like not unusual interest, commonplace interests and commonplace occupations can also help to foster their brotherhood. In Quran Allah says,

Believers are not else than brothers. (Surah Al-Hujurat- Verse No 10)

Relative Value in Islam

In Islam family is considered as a fundamental unit of human culture and the establishment of family is laid through marriage. The relationship between children, husband and wife should be everlasting and strong. Islam has given a duty to man to give financial support to his family whereas the duty of his wife is to look after her children and home. Holy prophet Muhammad (Sallallahu Alaihi Wasallam) noted once,

The best one among you is he who treats the members of his family best.

Acquaintances price in Islam

Allah Almighty lays exceptional pressure on kindness closer to friends, and inside the identical way the treatment of the bad. In Islam orphans have been made the objects of particular care. Islam makes the responsibility to be an amazing relation with dad and mom. Outstanding characteristic of Islam is merging all sections of society right into a single community so that each one men and women may feel themselves to be a member of the only family. Islam also encourages easy ways of life and deny with artificial requirements of living. In Quran Allah says,

Flip no longer your face far from humans in pride, nor stroll inside the earth proudly; Allah loves now not any smug guy. Moderate your feet at the same time as strolling and melt your voices while speaking something. (Surah Luqman – Verse No 18)

Justice in Islam

Equality in Islam additionally implies giving equivalent rights and remedy to other people. Equality an ethical ethicalness and a function of human person. Equality is nearer to balance as in it makes a circumstance of stability in conveyance of rights and duties, but they are not indistinguishable. The Prophet (noticed) declared approximately justice in Islam: "There are seven categories of human beings whom God will refuge underneath His coloration on the Day when there could be no coloration besides His. (One is) the simply chief"

Ethical cost

Islam has given a few ordinary fundamental rights of people as an entire, which are to be respected and found under all kinds of situation. To get these rights Islam presents a totally powerful ethical approaches. so anything leads to the welfare of the person or the society is morally precise in Islam and whatever is injurious is morally worst. Islam offers so much significance to the love of Allah and love of individual that is warns again and again of formalism. We recite in the Quran.

actuality, it isn't always righteousness that you switch our face towards east or west however it is righteousness is to trust in Allah and the day of judgment and the Holy Books and the angles and the messengers, out of love for him, for orphans, for the wayfarer, for the needy, for the ones asks and for the freeing of captives to be resolute of their supplications and they every day in doing suitable reason, and be

firm and affected person in anguish or enduring all through all instances of agonies the human beings of the God-conscious and truth. (Surah Al- Baqara- Verse No 177)

Quran has given a stunning description of the God-aware and righteous guy in above verses that he has to obey salutary policies, however he needs to restore his gaze on the affection of God and the love for human beings.

Allah Almighty has given 4 heads in above verses:

- a) Our faith must be sincere and real.
- b) We need to be organized to show the charity to our fellow-men.
- c) We need to be desirable residents and have to assist social agencies.
- d) Our own soul ought to be company and unshaken in all conditions.

The Quran has mentioned God-consciousness as the highest first-class of Muslims.

Most honorable among you inside the sight of Allah is maximum God-conscious. (Surah Al- Hujurat-Verse No 13)

Kindness In Islam

Islam lays a great emphasis on unique acts of kindness and define the obligations and rights of infinite relationship of humans. Our first responsibility is to appearance after our own family as mother and father, kids, husband, and wife. Then the alternative family, pals, buddies and acquaintances, orphans and widowers, the needy, our fellow Muslims brothers, all our fellow man or women and animals as nicely. Unique appreciate and take care of mother and father is very an awful lot stressed I the Islamic teaching and very vital a part of a Muslim's religion. As Allah ordered in Holy Quran.

Your God has decreed which you should not worship but him, and that your dad and mom have to be honored. so long as one or each of them gain old age for your lifetime, do not say to them a phrase of Uff or repel them, however must deal with them in term of honor. And, decrease to them the wing of humility and say, O my God; mercy on them, as they mercy on me in my infancy. (Surah Bani Israel-Verse No 23-24)

In keeping with Quran and Sunnah, a Muslim has to fulfill his ethical responsibility no longer best to family and friends however also to the whole humanity, animals and flora. Like, searching of birds and animals for the sake of recreation is illegitimate. Within the identical manner cutting timber and flowers, which yield fruit, isn't permitted until there may be a totally intense want for it. Islam has present better device of morality by means of virtue of which mankind can recognize its finest ability.

Economical Values:

Consistent with the Holton (1992) the fundamental principles of liberal economics represent thoughts derived from a large variety of source. Greater economist is also protected in it, like the 18t century economist Adan smith, and greater recent professional such as Milton Friedman (2000). The primary principle of this way of life consists of the subsequent areas.

- a) The rights of personal assets of human beings
- b) Self hobby in shopping
- c) Market of self-regulating
- d) The rationality

In information, values or movement on this regard are not in themselves taken into consideration as a rational. Islam has personal manner of thinking about life consistent with want the Muslim's lifestyles in this international is temporary section as examine to his everlasting life hereafter.

But usually seek the homestead of life hereafter in that which Allah has given you overlook now not your proportion of this international. (Surah Al – Qasas – Verse No 28)

Islam has provided sufficient within your means values to manual the humans. firstly, Islam rejects this fake idea that faith and economy are pretty one-of-a-kind ways and alternate is just an exchange and not anything else. In Quran Allah say,

O guy who believes while the decision is hard for the prayer of the day of congregation gather for remembrance of Allah and go away, you're buying and selling straight away. a good way to be higher for you if you recognize. And don't forget whilst the prayer is ended, then dispute into the earth and seek of Allah's bless, and bear in mind Allah a lot that you may get fulfillment. (Surah Al- Jumma- Verse No nine-10)

Religious Values of Islam

As the Caliph of Allah, a person needs to be capable of fulfill his undertaking in the direction of his duties. Inside the Holy Quran Allah has referred the Muslim because the best network amongst mankind and Islam seeks to accumulate the Muslims as the model for the whole humanity. The primary and primary spiritual duty of man is provided prayer 5 time a day. Islam has given an outstanding pressure on it. In Quran we recite,

Installed worship on the time of taking place of the sun until the darkish of night and the recitation of the Quran at down is ever witnessed, and some part of the nights also wide awake for it, a largess for them. it can be that Allah will raise them to a praised estate. (Surah Al-Bani-Israel-Verse No seventy-nine)

- ❖ For obligation of Zakat the recitation of Quran is,

You found him who neglects faith that is he, who neglects the orphans, and urgent now not the feeding of the needy. (Surah Al-Maghoon- Verse number 1-3)

❖ For jihad, by self and wealth or by pen Allah says,

Ye, you fight within the way of Allah in opposition to individuals who fight towards Muslims, however not start hostilities. Lo Allah does not love aggressions. (Surah AL-Baqara- Verse No one hundred ninety)

Political Value in Islam

he political beliefs of Islam clean that Allah Almighty is superb energy and writer of fellows and all matters present in the international, are useful for guys, as Allah says,

All belongs to him, something is within the heavens, whatever is in the earth, and anything is in between them, anything is underneath of sod. (Surah Al-Taha-Verse No 6)

Literature Review

- Ahmed & Sharif (1963) say that the educational convention in 1947 decided that the newly education device in born the United States of America that would be Find on Islamic coaching as it might be very obliging inspire and social integration in our society.
- Noor khan (1969) also highlight the function of Islamic training and introduce the ideological country and. could be recognized by using the kingdom of identity among the arena.
- Arifa (2013) highlights that there's require paintings to see for my part fulfillment of this subject in our classes.
- Authorities of Pakistan (1972) realized the significance of Islamic schooling and this is why it has been compulsory in secondary stages. Riaz (2017) writes that Islamic training is not meant to train the decrease instructions but it wishes to be made compulsory for all classes and our entire publications must be based totally on Islamic teaching.
- Zaher (2012) say that Islamic research become made obligatory on all secondary and higher secondary levels of Muslims college students as a way to sell integration and coherence among them. On the basis of Islamic ideology, we can upgrade a state of Islamic Ideology and its research desires
- Riaz (2014) state that collect the Qur'an and Nazira as a compulsory problem and taught with explanation the verses of Holy Qur'an with translation.
- Arifa (2013) country, that lifestyles a Muslims we already almost regarded approximately fundamental information of the Islam, in order that challenge of Islamic studies is not difficult subjects with evaluate to other topics like, Physics, Chemistry, Math or many other topics. The newbies can without problems understand these subjects in easiest manner.
- Jalindery (2012) says that that the teacher face issue while college students lack simple expertise of the Holy Quran and aren't capable of examine/recite the Qur'an in a accurate way. They're both shy and do not want to show their shortcomings before teacher are other students. Those styles of college students cover themselves behind clouds and take no hobby in the training and feel at the back of subsequently.
- Saad (1980) says that it (the concern) plays essential position in individual building. So, that is a superb difficulty if trainer teaches it without a doubt along with his heart and soul inside the paintings having full command on the concern. it could trade the character of the scholars from awful things and force to pursue the proper path.
- The Islamic schooling additionally help our community to like their United States of America and take duties on their shoulder.in the work having full command on the subject. It could change the nature of the students from bad things and force to pursue the right path.
- The Islamic education also help our community to love their country and take responsibilities on their shoulder.

Research Methodology

Problem Statement

Though Islamic education is an obligatory difficulty in Pakistan and its position as a catalytic in character constructing can't be unnoticed. In spite of its blessings Islamic training is given less priority as compared to different topics in our organization. This research will similarly look into college students' perspective approximately Islamic education as a topic that builds character.

Research Objective

- ❖ To provide the coaching of Holy Quran as the number of sources of education
- ❖ To provide experiences which can be based on basic of Islam as embodies in Holy Quran and Sunnah which cannot be modified.
- ❖ To assure the Islamic research as a obligatory difficulty.

Methodology

This study is essentially studying base approach which protected via evaluation of existing literature, article, and studies paper and one-of-a-kind websites inside the given place. The researchers additionally accrued

information from micro, small companies in Pakistan to contribute to empirical findings. The statistics had been accrued from one-of-a-kind websites and articles. Hence this take a look at is

“Record evaluation” a way of quantitative research in which many varieties of files are take a look at with the aid of research to modify the real explication of Islamic education in Pakistan. (7,8)

Data Analysis for Islamic Education in Pakistan

Pakistan is unbiased kingdom in 1947. The message for the contributor’s the founder of United States is said, there may be no uncertainty that the future of our kingdom definitely depends upon the schooling type that we supply the children and the alternative technique wherein we pick them as a destiny of Pakistani citizen” (9). At the time of independence problem was founded renovation of ideology Pakistan to be next generations. Hence in keeping with Lingered & Ali (10), at that to specify the function of Islam in curriculum and preparation. Due to the fact that, Pakistan came into being as a native land of Muslim Indians; the location of Islam in training are usually excessive. After independence of 1947 the Mr. Fazlur Rehman stated in conference;” I consider it of vital importance that our schooling gadget should be animated at guided by using these precept” (eleven).

At the same time as emphasizing upon nitty-gritties for schooling device of Pakistan he in addition reiterated (12); “our tutorial regulations ought to be regarding to the modern necessities and additionally throwback the ideas rely upon formation of Pakistan. The academic system could have been given guiding principle from Islamic ideas. It is best Islam at some stage in college of mind which presents a whole code of human sympathy and unity”.

After this conference in 1959 a fee become constituted to reform existing machine of education in United States. The country fee said that; “our tutorial gadget ought to play vital function for protecting those theories through which Pakistan came into being. Battle for Pakistan become absolutely shaping a route for protection of Islamic manner of existence (thirteen)”. therefore, the fee propose that measured to be followed to train citizen in such a manner that Islamic cost and rules may be determine among them to allow for the duration of their live consistent with Islam (14). furthermore, the commission improving religious training via education. It turned into suggested that non secular schooling has to offer in three ranges i.e., obligatory, non-compulsory and studies based totally (15). In same manner, the primary goal turned into Islamic training that each one the middle stage of students taught the various subjects that consist of Qur’an with (Nazira and translation), seerat-Ul-Nabi, Muslim literature and history for basic (16). In keeping with the policy foremost objective of those goal have been to create the feel some of the participants of Islamic international of Pakistani country. To construct and orientate the character of students according to Qur’an and Hadith so that they would be sincere and faithful Muslim.

To acquire these goals, the variety of innovative measures. Some of these are listed Islamiyat could be blanketed in all level of academics, technical and professional institution as a compulsory subject. In all schools and university, the teaching of Arabic will be organized. Changes might be introduced up in the curriculum and textual content-books in keeping with the precept and concept of Islam. The vital status will be given to mosque and five thousand mosque faculties will be hooked up for college students. All Madrassahs, Maktabs and Darul-Uloom will be given full importance and all of the leaner’s in Madras’s could be furnished equal schooling like different academic institutions. In 2009 the schooling coverage, is the contemporary attempt for enhancing education gadget of use and constructed it agreeable with relaxation of worldwide without understand the Islamic thoughts and values. The device specializing in “infusing Islamic and religious teaching in curriculum, in which as appropriate”.

Finding

- ❖ Most of the scholars agreed that the classes allotted for Islamic training want to be given choice.
- ❖ Maximum of the pupil agreed that the Islamic education allows students to increase their thirst for expertise.
- ❖ Maximum of college students agreed that the Islamic education play s vital position in individual constructing of students.
- ❖ Maximum of college students agreed that the Islamic schooling makes the pupil responsible to their society.
- ❖ Most of the scholars agreed that the Islamic schooling allows the scholars to come to be an awesome citizen.
- ❖ Maximum of the students agreed that Islamic training has a terrific effect at the social alternate of college students.
- ❖ Maximum of the scholars agreed that the Islamic study enables college students to stand the demanding situations of life without problems.
- ❖ Majority of student agreed that instructions of Islamic studies are frequently organized within the last durations.
- ❖ Majority of students do no longer attend the training of Islamic education.
- ❖ Lessons of Islamic schooling are demoted via the management.

- ❖ Majority of students agreed that the problem allocated marks in entry exams, so students are inquisitive about this situation.
- ❖ Majority of the scholars agreed that take it easy.
- ❖ More number of college students agreed that the lecturers of Islamic education show true manners.
- ❖ Maximum number of college students agreed that with their teacher's methodology.
- ❖ Highest variety of the student agreed that the trainer explains importance of Islamic schooling earlier than the students.
- ❖ most of the students agreed that students have already tons expertise so they may be over confident approximately this challenge

Objective of Islamic Education

- ❖ the principal intention of Islamic education for a separately and society are under:
- ❖ Coaching of Holy Qur'an is essential for all degrees of education.
- ❖ To explore understanding without the idea in faith and faith is incomplete training.
- ❖ Islam teaches the moral cost which can be universally normal by using society and are rooted in faith in religion.
- ❖ As a way of making college students feel responsible closer to God, so that they can stay their lives like trustworthy servants.
- ❖ To research how Pakistani's culture and religion form the instructional gadget nowadays.
- ❖ College students can be furnished with reports which are primarily based on the standards of Islam located in Holy Quran, and therefore cannot be changed.
- ❖ Islam increase the characteristics of a good man which can be recognized by using a society and are accepted by means of its membership.
- ❖ To are seeking out and discover the ones reports that can be gain college students, that are depend upon basics of Islamic faith as symbolize within the Holy Qur'an and cannot by no means alternate.
- ❖ Within the light of Islamic philosophy and fulfillment, study academic philosophy and achievement.

Way Forward

Being Pakistan as an Islamic country, our whole instructional machine have to be organized consistent with Islamic values and civilization. In keeping with the Islamic lifestyle, background and values its far responsibility of nation to unfold Islam and enhance training to reinforce the society. Instructional regulations have to not best continue to be in paper form but several steps ought to be taken for giving practical coloration to those guidelines. It ought to be cited in regulations that from number one stage till higher education it is important to train the people according to Islamic values especially to secondary degree to build toddler's individual undoubtedly. Secondary degree schooling must be identified. All the defects need to be covered by way of the authority's instructional department. Mainly the curriculum making plans committee have to take realistic steps for protecting all Islamic knowledge in curriculum according to the inspiration of tutorial regulations. In educational regulations the position of parents, instructors, textual content books and society in selling Islamic information amongst college students additionally be highlighted. For the reason that schooling coverage of Holy Quran, is being taunt with translation in Pakistani faculties. Curriculum become revised via a number of instances to house religious sectors and to meet different pressure corporations worrying drastic changes primarily based upon Islamic rituals. Madrasa reform had made its effect and extra than ten thousand madras are registered with the authorities where 1. Nine million students are enrolled (28).

Conclusion

Special secondary colleges in Pakistan have extraordinary syllabuses for their secondary education packages. Inside the private faculties, Islamic training is a compulsory situation, however, it specially covers Islamic teachings, while in authority's colleges, Islamic schooling similarly to numerous obligatory and non-compulsory subjects. the main causes of effectiveness of the Islamic studies at secondary stage except monetary problems are the much less interest of the mother and father, separate circle of relatives machine, negative role of media, mother and father are busy of their jobs, incomplete material approximately Islamic values in textual content books, all topics don't have any reference to Islamic values, non-sincerity of the teachers in professional schooling etc. on the other hand, schooling machine inside the conventional spiritual schools referred to as madrasas or madras or Islamic spiritual colleges. There are numerous verses of the Quran and Sunnah of the prophet highlighted the position of learned persons. A found-out scholar in his remark on Holy Quran writes that if a man can be fearless of Allah to be quantity of his ignorance of attributes of Allah. On the other a person who know the attributes of Allah, he might be terrified of his disobedience. Consequently, a median who is not scared of Allah, he absolutely does no longer possess information despite the fact that he has attained obvious expertise. It's far reasonable that the usual of Islamic education gifted to human scenario to the most noteworthy manufacturing of Allah. Educators are the standards planners of training. At the depend the guidance of understudies alongside Islamic traces and producing of an Islamic soul in them. Allah has conceded the Muslim

are best Ummah who spread actually faith in Allah who at the least would gain in the blessing of Allah on the planet and akhirat.

Bibliography Reference

- United Nations (1999) Optional Protocol to the Convention On the Elimination of Discrimination against Muslims.*
- Action', United Nations(1993) World Conference on Human Rights 'Vienna Declaration and programme of.
- Ali, Y. 1989.*The Meaning of the Holy Qur'an*. s.l. : Amana corporation, 1989.
- Andarbi, T.,Das,J.,Khuwaja and Zajonc,T. 2006.*Religious school enrollment in pakistan* . 2006.
- Anzar, U. April, 2008.*Islamic education: A brief history of madrasses with comments on curricula and current pedagogical practices*. April, 2008.
- Azami, Iqbal Ahmed. *Muslim Manner: A Guide for parents and Educators of Muslim Children*, Leicester, England: UK Islamic Academy, 1990.
- Bassiouni, Cherif, M.S Dakkak and A.Wazir, eds. 1 *Human Rights: International Regional Instrument*. Dar-ilm lil- Malayan, 1998.
- Be masters in that you teach and continue to learn:Medieval Muslim thinker on educational theory*. Guenther, S. (2006). 2003. 2003.
- Boyle, H. 2006.*Memorization and learning in islamic schools*. 2006.
- Dahir, Mubarak S."*Not A Prayer - A Muslim Boy's School Days in the Bible Beh.*"*Church & state* 48 (March 1995).
- Eck, Diana L."*Muslims in America:Forming the Next Generation* ." *Christan Century* 118, no. 18 (2001): 20-25.
- Esack, Farid. " In Search of Progressive Islam Beyond 9/11." In *Progressive Muslims*, edited by Imid Safi, 78-97. Oxford:Oneworld Publications,2003.
- Fair, Carol Christine. 2006.*Islamic Education in Pakistan*. 2006.
- Gender disparities, economics groth and islamzation in pakitan*. coleman, I. (2004). 2004. 2004.
- Mohammad Johdi sallah, Ph.D. 2009.*Integrated islamic education*. Singapore : s.n., 2009.
- Pakistan (1951) The Pakistan Citizenship Act*.
- Pakistan (1860) the Pakistan Panel Code*.
- Pakistan (1984) the Qanum-e-Shahadat Order [Evidence Act]*.
- Rameez. 2018.*Role of Islamic education*. Sindh : s.n., 2018.
- saleem, Dr khalid. 2014.*Islamization of education in pakistan*. karachi : muhammed saeed, 2014.
- 1973.*The constituion of Pakistan*. Pakistan: s.n., 1973.
- United Nation (1966) *International convenat on Ecniomics, Social and culture Rights*.
- United Nations (1945) The Charter of the Unitrd Nation*. .
- United Nations (1984) Convention against Torture and Other cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or punishment*.
- Waqar, Dr. 2012.*Consideration of ilamic values in Educational policies of Pakistan*. 2012.

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